

Financial services post-demonetization

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Abstract

The Indian government discontinued Rs.1000 and Rs.500 notes with immediate effect due to demonetization on 9th November 2016. The aftermath was the knee jerk effect on merchants, transportation, and logistics, which was affected by cash shortage and caused a small financial upheaval for the retail market as people in India are mostly used to cash transactions for their everyday life and to turn towards cashless modes of payment was a bit painful for starters. However, this move has eventually boosted the banking sector reforms with digital linkage, enhanced transparency in financial transactions, and managed to curb black money and corruption to some extent. The present review has exemplified that post demonetization; the foreign investment infrastructure has not been affected positively. The banking financial services have seen an upgrade with increased bank accounts being opened; digital transactions, i.e., internet banking; digital wallets, have changed people's use of financial services. Tax collection by the government has improved. More people have started saving and investing in mutual funds. However, conversely, cyber frauds and security problems have also cropped up due to internet transactions' heightened use.

Keywords: Demonetization, Financial services, Post-demonetization impact

Introduction

On 9th November 2016, Rs.1000 and Rs.500 notes were discontinued effect immediately due to demonetization. The results of demonetization have been worthy enough from the banking sector's point of view. The usage of financial accounts has gone up to fifty-one percent from the normal thirty-four percent pre-demonetization even the post office accounts increased due to the demonetization. It was found that this incident increased financial inclusion among women, mostly from rural areas (van de Waal, 2017).

Then again, the aftermath was a knee jerk effect on merchants, transportation, and logistics that were affected by cash shortage, which caused a small financial upheaval for the retail market as people in India are mostly used to cash transactions for their everyday life and to turn towards cashless modes of payment was very slow and painful. Nevertheless, people also realized that it was a beneficial step towards stopping black money circulation in the country to some extent (van de Waal, 2017).

Albeit, demonetization in India in 2016 was aimed at boosting the banking sector reforms with digital linkage, enhancing transparency in financial transactions, curbing black money and corruption. However, it has also affected the GDP, daily wage earner in the industrial sector, and the real estate market (Ganesan and Gajendranayagam, 2017). Therefore, this review plans to study the various nuances in India's financial services post-demonetization and comprehend its effects on its population on the ground.

Literature Review

The stock market in India has both domestic and foreign investors, and it was found that FII's and DII's were not significantly impacted post demonetization as even before demonetization, the Nifty 50 index returns had a negative correlation with FII's and DII's and post-demonetization also it was quite severely affected (Joo and Mir., 2104).

The banking sector has played a key role in the economic development of the country. However, post-demonetization, the customers' discernment towards the banks has changed. Furthermore, the banks lately have been struggling with NPA's (non-performing assets) in both the public and the private sectors about 8.27 lakh crores. However, on the positive side, it has helped to link Aadhar card and Pan card for taxation purposes and has supported digital services for government programs (Rao and Suvarchala, 2018).

A study conducted by Rao and Suvarchala (2018) in Andhra Pradesh elicited the following results: 52% held accounts in the public sector banks and 48 in the private sector, males dominated the sample 61.5% and females at 28.5%. There is a statistically significant difference among males and females towards the financial services offered by the bank, and it is as follows: post – demonetization, there has been an improved acceptance of new banking techniques involving computers; increase in availing the banking services frequency per month, greater than before ATM, and mobile banking services use per month, etc. The customers have changed their opinions on the banks operating without computers; charges imposed have reduced post-demonetization, use of mobile apps for banking services, sending monthly statements on emails, education on internet banking, other online services, information on SMS, etc. have improved the satisfaction of the customers overall in the post-demonetization era. On the downside, internet banking services have also increased cyber frauds and deficient liquidity in the banking services (Rao and Suvarchala, 2018).

After the demonetization, the digital modes of banking have become very popular in India. This can be attributed to the uncomfortable days that ensued after demonetization, i.e., the shortage of cash, especially larger denominations like new 500 and 2000 rupee notes, people having to rush to the banks for exchanging their notes and the rationing of cash withdrawals, the long queues, etc. (Pachare, 2016)

In India, with its population of approximately seven billion, the statistics for owning mobile phones are skewed to 70% compared to only 30% with bank accounts and even pre- demonetization. This has led to many people using digital modes of payment, and digital wallets are now exceptionally popular with the masses for paying for groceries, money transfer for business (38%), paying bills and recharge (30%), and utilities (12 %) (Pachare, 2016). Digital wallets are a mobile or personal computer application linked to one's bank account, and it is a pre-paid instrument where one can easily receive or transfer money in minutes. For example, Paytm, ICICI pockets, PayUMoney, etc., and this market, post-demonetization is forecasted to be 6.6 billion dollars by 2020 (Pachare, 2016). However, the issues commonly associated with digital wallets are: deficiency of NFC enabled terminals, security concerns, and lack of standard technology.

Ganesan and Gajendranayagam (2017) have mentioned in their study that demonetization has definitely benefitted the banks, and almost ninety percent is back into circulation. It has helped the RBI decrease its obligations, reduce the lending rates, and pass these benefits to its consumers. The government has also benefitted at all levels as more taxes can now be collected due to more deposits in the banks, and according to CRISIL, it(government) can now invest more in infrastructure and have a better go at growth and development in the country due to more efficient tax collection system.

The table given below has given a window into many countries' past demonetization efforts, mainly to reduce corruption. The result was that this move had not been taken well by most third world and developing countries.

Table 1 History of countries with demonetization (Countries that have tried Demonetization in the past)

Country	Year	Impact
USA	1873	1873 Demonetization-removed silver and replaced it with gold standard as legal tender this led to 5 year economic depression
USA	1969	Declared more than 100\$ bills null and void- impacted as better development of American Banking System
India	1978	10,000, 1000, 500 notes removed no negative impact as such on people's lives as these notes were less in circulation anyways
Ghana	1982	Demonetized 50 cedi notes- the impact was that it was very unsuccessful as it increased corruption and people lost confidence in the bank
Nigeria	1984	Introduced different coloured notes, but it failed to revive the debt ridden economy
Myanmar	1987	Military invalidated 80 percent of the money in circulation led to vast unrest
USSR	1991	50 and 100 rouble notes were demonetized- led to loss of faith in the government
Zaire	1993	Demonetization disrupted the government
Australia	1996	Paper based notes replaced by polymer based notes was successful with increased costs of transition but helped it as a business nation
EU	2002	Demonetized existing currencies of 12 countries with slow transition from 1998 – very successful move due to prior information to the citizens.
North Korea	2010	Demonetization increased prices of essential goods; strongly resisted by people
Zimbabwe	2015	Replacement of Zimbabwe dollar with American dollar highly unsuccessful as it affected the rich people with adverse effect on the economy

Impact of financial services in India post demonetization:

Following are some of the highlights of the impact of financial services in India post demonetization:

- POS(point of sale machines have increased 1.6 million since the past 20 years after demonetization, i.e., within six months after demonetization, there was a sixty-two percent increase (Nilekani, 2017)
- Digital transactions increased to 113 crores, i.e., 60 percent increase.
- In six months Aadhar enabled transactions increased from 2.5 crores to 5 crores (Vij, 2018)

- Gross national disposable income increased from 10.6% to 11.8%, and people have started saving more, and investments in mutual funds have increased 155%, i.e., 3.43 lakh crores (Vij, 2018)

Conclusion

The present review has exemplified that post demonetization; the foreign investment infrastructure has not been affected positively. The banking financial services have seen an upgrade with increased bank accounts being opened; digital transactions, i.e., internet banking; digital wallets, have changed people's use of financial services. Tax collection by the government has improved. More people have started saving and investing in mutual funds. However, conversely, cyber frauds and security problems have also cropped up due to internet transactions' heightened use.

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